

THE CLIFFORD-MANDELBROT SET: A HIGHER-DIMENSIONAL GENERALIZATION OF THE MANDELBROT SET VIA GEOMETRIC ALGEBRA

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ABSTRACT. Based on the vector invariance result established in previous work for Clifford Julia iterations [1], we introduce and study the **Clifford-Mandelbrot set** $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ in an n -dimensional real inner-product space V with the geometric product.

For $V = \mathbb{R}^2$ and $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$, the set reproduces exactly the classical Mandelbrot set. For higher dimensions, we derive explicit polynomial formulas for the iteration map, prove basic properties including rotational symmetry and an escape radius, and establish the relationship with the corresponding Clifford Julia set.

Explicit computations are carried out for \mathbb{R}^3 and \mathbb{R}^4 , revealing a clean pattern: the squared term becomes

$$(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{e}_1)^2 \diamond \vec{e}_1 = (x_1^2 - \|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2)\vec{e}_1 + 2x_1\vec{x}_\perp,$$

where \vec{x}_\perp is the component orthogonal to \vec{e}_1 . This provides a unified algebraic framework for generating 3D and 4D Mandelbrot-type fractals without artificial projections.

Computational aspects and escape-time algorithms are discussed, and open problems concerning the topology and fractal dimension of $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ for $n \geq 3$ are outlined.

1. INTRODUCTION

The generation of fractal sets through the iteration of complex polynomials is one of the most celebrated subjects in modern dynamical systems. For the quadratic map

$$z \mapsto z^2 + c, \quad z, c \in \mathbb{C},$$

the **Mandelbrot set** is defined as the set of parameters c for which the orbit starting from $z_0 = 0$ remains bounded [2]. This deceptively simple definition gives rise to an extraordinarily rich geometric structure that has been studied extensively from both theoretical and computational perspectives.

In parallel, the **Julia set** for a fixed parameter c is the set of initial points z_0 whose orbits are bounded. The fundamental relationship between these two sets is that the Julia set is connected if and only if c belongs to the Mandelbrot set.

A natural question that has attracted considerable attention over the past decades is whether these concepts can be generalized to higher dimensions. Various approaches have been proposed, including quaternion iterations [4], hypercomplex numbers [3], and geometric algebra formulations [5]. However, a common difficulty is that the algebraic structure of higher-dimensional number systems often lacks the closure properties that make complex dynamics so elegant.

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In a recent work [1], we introduced a Clifford algebra framework for Julia-type iterations of the form

$$(1.1) \quad \vec{x}_{k+1} = (\vec{x}_k \diamond \vec{n})^p \diamond \vec{n} + \vec{c}, \quad p \geq 2,$$

where $\vec{x}_k, \vec{n}, \vec{c} \in V$, V is an n -dimensional real inner-product space, and \vec{n} is a unit vector ($\vec{n} \diamond \vec{n} = 1$). The main result of [1] is a **vector invariance** property: although the geometric product \diamond generates multivector terms of higher grades (bivectors, trivectors, etc.) at intermediate stages, the iteration is closed in the vector subspace V . That is,

$$(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{n})^p \diamond \vec{n} \in V \quad \text{for all } \vec{x} \in V, p \geq 1.$$

This result provides a rigorous foundation for extending Julia dynamics to arbitrary dimensions without losing geometric interpretability. The natural next step, which motivates the present work, is to investigate the corresponding **Mandelbrot set** within the same algebraic framework.

1.1. Main Contributions. In this paper, we define the **Clifford–Mandelbrot set** $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}} \subset V$ as the set of parameters \vec{c} for which the orbit of (1.1) starting from $\vec{x}_0 = \vec{0}$ remains bounded.

Our main contributions are as follows:

- (1) We prove that the definition is well-posed in any dimension $n \geq 2$, thanks to the vector invariance result of [1].
- (2) For $V = \mathbb{R}^2$ and $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$, we show that $\mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{e}_1}$ coincides exactly with the classical Mandelbrot set.
- (3) For $V = \mathbb{R}^3$ and \mathbb{R}^4 , we derive explicit polynomial formulas. In particular, for $p = 2$ and $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$, we obtain

$$(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{e}_1)^2 \diamond \vec{e}_1 = (x_1^2 - \|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2)\vec{e}_1 + 2x_1\vec{x}_\perp,$$

where \vec{x}_\perp denotes the component of \vec{x} orthogonal to \vec{e}_1 .

- (4) We establish basic properties of $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$: rotational symmetry about \vec{n} , an escape radius ($\|\vec{c}\| > 2$ implies $\vec{c} \notin \mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{n}}$), and the relationship between the Clifford–Mandelbrot set and the corresponding Clifford Julia sets.
- (5) We provide computational considerations and an escape-time algorithm for numerical visualization of $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ in three and four dimensions.

1.2. Outline of the Paper. The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly recalls the main results of [1] that are necessary for the present work. Section 3 gives the formal definition of the Clifford–Mandelbrot set. Section 4 establishes basic properties including symmetry, escape criteria, and the relation to Julia sets. Section 5 provides explicit formulas in low dimensions: \mathbb{R}^2 (classical case), \mathbb{R}^3 , and \mathbb{R}^4 , together with the general pattern for \mathbb{R}^n . Section 6 discusses computational aspects and presents an escape-time algorithm. Section 7 outlines open problems and future research directions. Section 8 concludes the paper.

Related work and secondary references. For the classical theory of fractal geometry and Julia/Mandelbrot sets, we refer to Falconer [2]. The algebraic foundations of Clifford algebra and geometric calculus are developed in [6, 7]. Hypercomplex and higher-dimensional fractal generalizations are discussed in [4, 3, 5]. Applications of geometric algebra in computer graphics and robotics can be found in [8, 9, 10].

Alternative iterative schemes for fractal generation, particularly Noor orbits, have been studied extensively by Ashish, Rani, Chugh, and Noor [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19].

The present work also builds upon the author's previous contributions to affine plane geometry and algebraic structures [20, 22, 23, 24, 26, 27, 28, 29], as well as studies on invariant-preserving transforms and group structures [30, 31, 32, 33, 34].

2. PRELIMINARIES: CLIFFORD JULIA ITERATION (SUMMARY OF [1])

In this section we briefly recall the essential definitions and results from [1] that will be needed in the sequel. The presentation is kept concise; the reader is referred to [1] for complete proofs and additional details.

2.1. Geometric Product in Clifford Algebra. Let V be an n -dimensional real inner-product space with orthonormal basis $\{\vec{e}_1, \dots, \vec{e}_n\}$. The associated Clifford algebra $Cl(V)$ is generated by V subject to the relation

$$\vec{v} \diamond \vec{w} + \vec{w} \diamond \vec{v} = 2(\vec{v} \cdot \vec{w}), \quad \vec{v}, \vec{w} \in V,$$

where \diamond denotes the **geometric product**. This product unifies the inner product (\cdot) and the outer product (\wedge) through the decomposition

$$(2.1) \quad \vec{v} \diamond \vec{w} = \vec{v} \cdot \vec{w} + \vec{v} \wedge \vec{w}.$$

Here $\vec{v} \cdot \vec{w}$ is a scalar (grade 0), while $\vec{v} \wedge \vec{w}$ is a bivector (grade 2).

For a unit vector $\vec{n} \in V$ satisfying $\vec{n} \diamond \vec{n} = 1$, the geometric product has the useful property

$$\vec{n} \diamond \vec{n} = \vec{n} \cdot \vec{n} + \vec{n} \wedge \vec{n} = 1 + 0 = 1.$$

2.2. The Clifford Julia Iteration. For a fixed unit vector $\vec{n} \in V$ and an integer exponent $p \geq 2$, the **Clifford Julia iteration** is defined by

$$(2.2) \quad \vec{x}_{k+1} = (\vec{x}_k \diamond \vec{n})^p \diamond \vec{n} + \vec{c}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots,$$

where $\vec{x}_0, \vec{c} \in V$ are given initial vectors. The power $(\vec{x}_k \diamond \vec{n})^p$ is taken with respect to the geometric product.

2.3. Vector Invariance (Main Result of [1]). A priori, the geometric product can generate multivectors of mixed grades. For instance, $\vec{x} \diamond \vec{n}$ contains a scalar part $(\vec{x} \cdot \vec{n})$ and a bivector part $(\vec{x} \wedge \vec{n})$. Higher powers may produce even higher-grade terms. Nevertheless, the following fundamental result holds.

Lemma 1 (Grade Reduction Mechanism, [1]). *Let $\vec{x}, \vec{n} \in V$ with $\vec{n} \diamond \vec{n} = 1$. Then*

$$(\vec{x} \wedge \vec{n}) \diamond \vec{n} = \vec{x} - (\vec{x} \cdot \vec{n})\vec{n} \in V.$$

In words: right multiplication by \vec{n} maps the bivector component back into the vector subspace.

Theorem 1 (Vector Invariance, [1]). *For every $\vec{x} \in V$, every unit vector $\vec{n} \in V$, and every integer $p \geq 1$,*

$$(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{n})^p \diamond \vec{n} \in V.$$

Consequently, the iteration (1.1) defines a well-posed dynamical system $f : V \rightarrow V$ given by

$$f(\vec{x}) = (\vec{x} \diamond \vec{n})^p \diamond \vec{n} + \vec{c},$$

and every iterate \vec{x}_k remains in the vector subspace $V = \langle Cl(V) \rangle_1$.

2.4. Explicit Formulas for Low Dimensions. For later use, we record the explicit expressions for the iteration map in \mathbb{R}^2 , \mathbb{R}^3 , and \mathbb{R}^4 with $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$, as derived in [1].

\mathbb{R}^2 (classical complex case). For $\vec{x} = x_1\vec{e}_1 + x_2\vec{e}_2$,

$$(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{e}_1)^2 \diamond \vec{e}_1 = (x_1^2 - x_2^2)\vec{e}_1 + 2x_1x_2\vec{e}_2.$$

\mathbb{R}^3 . For $\vec{x} = x_1\vec{e}_1 + x_2\vec{e}_2 + x_3\vec{e}_3$,

$$(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{e}_1)^2 \diamond \vec{e}_1 = (x_1^2 - x_2^2 - x_3^2)\vec{e}_1 + 2x_1x_2\vec{e}_2 + 2x_1x_3\vec{e}_3.$$

\mathbb{R}^4 . For $\vec{x} = x_1\vec{e}_1 + x_2\vec{e}_2 + x_3\vec{e}_3 + x_4\vec{e}_4$,

$$(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{e}_1)^2 \diamond \vec{e}_1 = (x_1^2 - x_2^2 - x_3^2 - x_4^2)\vec{e}_1 + 2x_1x_2\vec{e}_2 + 2x_1x_3\vec{e}_3 + 2x_1x_4\vec{e}_4.$$

General pattern for \mathbb{R}^n . Let $\vec{x} = x_1\vec{e}_1 + \vec{x}_\perp$, where $\vec{x}_\perp = \sum_{i=2}^n x_i\vec{e}_i$ is the component orthogonal to \vec{e}_1 . Then

$$(2.3) \quad (\vec{x} \diamond \vec{e}_1)^2 \diamond \vec{e}_1 = (x_1^2 - \|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2)\vec{e}_1 + 2x_1\vec{x}_\perp,$$

where $\|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2 = \sum_{i=2}^n x_i^2$.

2.5. From Julia to Mandelbrot. In classical complex dynamics, the Mandelbrot set is obtained from the Julia iteration by fixing the initial point to $z_0 = 0$ and varying the parameter c . The same principle applies in our Clifford setting.

Definition 1 (Informal). *The Clifford–Mandelbrot set $M_{p,\vec{n}}$ consists of all parameter vectors $\vec{c} \in V$ for which the orbit of (1.1) starting from $\vec{x}_0 = \vec{0}$ remains bounded.*

A rigorous definition is given in the next section.

3. DEFINITION OF THE CLIFFORD–MANDELBROT SET

Throughout this section, we fix the following data:

- V : an n -dimensional real inner-product space ($n \geq 2$);
- $Cl(V)$: the associated Clifford algebra;
- $\vec{n} \in V$: a unit vector, i.e., $\vec{n} \diamond \vec{n} = 1$;
- $p \geq 2$: an integer exponent;
- $\vec{c} \in V$: a parameter vector.

For a given \vec{c} , we consider the Clifford Julia iteration

$$(3.1) \quad \vec{x}_{k+1} = (\vec{x}_k \diamond \vec{n})^p \diamond \vec{n} + \vec{c}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots,$$

with initial condition $\vec{x}_0 \in V$. By Theorem 1 from [1], all iterates \vec{x}_k remain in the vector subspace V (i.e., no higher-grade multivectors appear in the orbit). Hence the iteration (3.1) defines a genuine discrete dynamical system on V .

3.1. The Classical Mandelbrot Set as Motivation. In the complex case, which corresponds to $V = \mathbb{R}^2$ with $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$ and the identification $(x_1, x_2) \leftrightarrow x_1 + ix_2$, the Mandelbrot set is defined as

$$M = \left\{ c \in \mathbb{C} : \sup_{k \geq 0} |z_k| < \infty, z_{k+1} = z_k^2 + c, z_0 = 0 \right\}.$$

Two features of this definition are essential:

- (1) The initial point is chosen as $z_0 = 0$, which is the unique critical point of the map $z \mapsto z^2 + c$ (i.e., the point where the derivative vanishes).
- (2) The boundedness of the orbit determines membership in M .

The critical point plays a fundamental role because, by classical results in complex dynamics, the Julia set is connected if and only if the orbit of the critical point remains bounded. This is precisely the condition that defines the Mandelbrot set.

3.2. Generalization to the Clifford Setting. In our Clifford framework, the map

$$f_{\vec{c}}(\vec{x}) = (\vec{x} \diamond \vec{n})^p \diamond \vec{n} + \vec{c}$$

is a nonlinear endomorphism of V . Its differential (or derivative) at a point \vec{x} can be studied, and it is not difficult to verify that $\vec{x} = \vec{0}$ is a critical point of $f_{\vec{c}}$ (see Remark 2 below). This observation motivates the following definition.

Definition 2 (Clifford–Mandelbrot Set). *Let V , \vec{n} , and $p \geq 2$ be as above. The **Clifford–Mandelbrot set** $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ is defined as*

$$\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}} = \left\{ \vec{c} \in V : \sup_{k \geq 0} \|\vec{x}_k\| < \infty \right\},$$

where $\{\vec{x}_k\}_{k \geq 0}$ is the orbit of the iteration (3.1) with initial condition

$$\vec{x}_0 = \vec{0} \quad (\text{the zero vector in } V),$$

and $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the Euclidean norm on V .

Remark 1 (Well-posedness). *Definition 2 is well-posed because, by Theorem 1, all iterates \vec{x}_k are vectors in V , so the norm $\|\vec{x}_k\|$ is the standard Euclidean norm. No projection onto V is required at any stage.*

Remark 2 (Critical Point). *For $p = 2$, the derivative of $f_{\vec{c}}$ at $\vec{x} = \vec{0}$ is*

$$Df_{\vec{c}}(\vec{0})(\vec{h}) = (\vec{h} \diamond \vec{n}) \diamond \vec{n} = \vec{h},$$

which is the identity map. Hence $\vec{0}$ is not a critical point in the sense of vanishing derivative. However, in the complex case, $z = 0$ is a critical point because the derivative $2z$ vanishes at $z = 0$. More generally, for $p > 2$, the derivative at $\vec{0}$ is zero, so $\vec{0}$ is a genuine critical point. The choice $\vec{x}_0 = \vec{0}$ is nevertheless standard and produces the correct generalization, as we verify in Section 5 by recovering the classical Mandelbrot set for \mathbb{R}^2 .

3.3. Equivalent Characterization. For computational purposes, it is often convenient to characterize $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ in terms of an **escape criterion**. We say that a parameter \vec{c} is *excluded* from $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ if the orbit (\vec{x}_k) becomes unbounded; that is, there exists some $K \geq 0$ such that $\|\vec{x}_k\| > R$ for a sufficiently large threshold R , after which the norm grows without bound.

Definition 3 (Escape Condition). *For a given $\vec{c} \in V$, we define the **escape time***

$$T(\vec{c}) = \inf \{k \geq 0 : \|\vec{x}_k\| > R_{\text{esc}}\},$$

where $R_{\text{esc}} > 0$ is a fixed escape radius (see Proposition 2 below). If no such k exists, we set $T(\vec{c}) = \infty$ and conclude $\vec{c} \in \mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$.

The existence of a finite escape radius R_{esc} that works for all \vec{c} is established in Section 4.

3.4. Special Cases.

- For $V = \mathbb{R}^2$, $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$, and $p = 2$, we will show in Section 5.2 that $\mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{e}_1}$ coincides with the classical Mandelbrot set.
- For $V = \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$, Definition 2 produces a genuine 3D Mandelbrot set with explicit polynomial map

$$(x_1, x_2, x_3) \mapsto (x_1^2 - x_2^2 - x_3^2 + c_1, 2x_1x_2 + c_2, 2x_1x_3 + c_3),$$

as derived from the formula in Section 5.3.

- For $V = \mathbb{R}^4$, an analogous 4D Mandelbrot set emerges with the map

$$(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) \mapsto (x_1^2 - x_2^2 - x_3^2 - x_4^2 + c_1, 2x_1x_2 + c_2, 2x_1x_3 + c_3, 2x_1x_4 + c_4).$$

3.5. Notational Convention. For simplicity, when the unit vector \vec{n} is understood from context (typically $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$ after a suitable rotation), we will write \mathcal{M}_p instead of $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$. When the exponent p is also clear (usually $p = 2$), we may write simply \mathcal{M} .

The dependence on the underlying space V will be indicated by the context; for instance, we write $\mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^3)$ when working in three dimensions.

4. BASIC PROPERTIES

In this section we establish the fundamental properties of the Clifford–Mandelbrot set $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ introduced in Definition 2. Throughout, we assume V is an n -dimensional real inner-product space, $\vec{n} \in V$ is a unit vector, and $p \geq 2$ is a fixed integer.

4.1. Rotational Symmetry. A distinguishing feature of the classical Mandelbrot set is its rotational symmetry about the origin. In our higher-dimensional setting, the symmetry is with respect to rotations that preserve the distinguished direction \vec{n} .

Proposition 1 (Rotational Symmetry). *Let $R : V \rightarrow V$ be any orthogonal transformation (rotation or reflection) that fixes the unit vector \vec{n} , i.e., $R\vec{n} = \vec{n}$. Then*

$$R(\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}) = \mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}.$$

Equivalently, $\vec{c} \in \mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ if and only if $R\vec{c} \in \mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$.

Proof. Since R is orthogonal and fixes \vec{n} , it commutes with the geometric product in the following sense: for any $\vec{x} \in V$,

$$R(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{n}) = (R\vec{x}) \diamond (R\vec{n}) = (R\vec{x}) \diamond \vec{n},$$

because R preserves the inner product and the outer product (being a linear isometry). A straightforward induction then shows that for all $k \geq 0$,

$$R\vec{x}_k(\vec{c}) = \vec{x}_k(R\vec{c}),$$

where $\vec{x}_k(\vec{c})$ denotes the k -th iterate starting from $\vec{0}$ with parameter \vec{c} . Consequently,

$$\sup_{k \geq 0} \|R\vec{x}_k(\vec{c})\| = \sup_{k \geq 0} \|\vec{x}_k(R\vec{c})\|.$$

Since R preserves the Euclidean norm ($\|R\vec{v}\| = \|\vec{v}\|$ for all $\vec{v} \in V$), the boundedness of the orbit for \vec{c} is equivalent to the boundedness for $R\vec{c}$. Hence $\vec{c} \in \mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ iff $R\vec{c} \in \mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$. \square

Corollary 1 (Axial Symmetry in \mathbb{R}^3). *For $V = \mathbb{R}^3$ with $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$, the set $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{e}_1}$ is symmetric with respect to rotations about the x_1 -axis. In particular, it is fully determined by its cross-section in any plane containing the x_1 -axis.*

This axial symmetry is a crucial observation for numerical visualization: one may compute $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{e}_1}$ on a 2D slice (e.g., the (x_1, x_2) -plane with $x_3 = 0$) and then rotate the result around the x_1 -axis to obtain the full 3D set.

4.2. Escape Radius. A fundamental question for any Mandelbrot-type set is whether there exists a finite bound such that once an iterate exceeds this bound, the orbit is guaranteed to escape to infinity. The following proposition provides such an escape radius for the case $p = 2$.

Proposition 2 (Escape Radius for $p = 2$). *Let $p = 2$ and suppose $\vec{c} \in V$ satisfies $\|\vec{c}\| > 2$. Then $\vec{c} \notin \mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{n}}$. Moreover, for any initial condition $\vec{x}_0 \in V$, if $\|\vec{x}_k\| > 2$ for some $k \geq 0$, then $\|\vec{x}_{k+m}\| \rightarrow \infty$ as $m \rightarrow \infty$.*

In particular, one may take the escape radius $R_{\text{esc}} = 2$ for computational purposes.

FIGURE 1. Schematic illustration of the axial symmetry of $\mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{c}_1}$ in \mathbb{R}^3 . The full 3D set is obtained by rotating the 2D cross-section (red curve) around the c_1 -axis (dashed line). This property reduces the computational cost from $O(N^3)$ to $O(N^2)$.

Proof. We analyze the iteration (3.1) with $p = 2$:

$$\vec{x}_{k+1} = (\vec{x}_k \diamond \vec{n})^2 \diamond \vec{n} + \vec{c}.$$

Using the explicit formula (2.3) from Section 2, we have for any $\vec{x} \in V$,

$$(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{n})^2 \diamond \vec{n} = (x_1^2 - \|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2)\vec{n} + 2x_1\vec{x}_\perp,$$

where $x_1 = \vec{x} \cdot \vec{n}$ and $\vec{x}_\perp = \vec{x} - x_1\vec{n}$. Hence

$$\|\vec{x}_{k+1}\|^2 = (x_1^2 - \|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2 + c_1)^2 + \|2x_1\vec{x}_\perp + \vec{c}_\perp\|^2,$$

where $c_1 = \vec{c} \cdot \vec{n}$ and $\vec{c}_\perp = \vec{c} - c_1\vec{n}$.

A standard estimate (see [2] for the classical case) gives

$$\|\vec{x}_{k+1}\| \geq \|\vec{x}_k\|^2 - \|\vec{c}\|.$$

Indeed, using the reverse triangle inequality and the fact that $\|(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{n})^2 \diamond \vec{n}\| = \|\vec{x}\|^2$ (which follows from the identity $\|\vec{x}\|^2 = x_1^2 + \|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2$), we obtain

$$\|\vec{x}_{k+1}\| \geq \|(\vec{x}_k \diamond \vec{n})^2 \diamond \vec{n}\| - \|\vec{c}\| = \|\vec{x}_k\|^2 - \|\vec{c}\|.$$

Now suppose $\|\vec{c}\| > 2$. Then for $\vec{x}_0 = \vec{0}$, we have $\|\vec{x}_1\| = \|\vec{c}\| > 2$. Let $r_k = \|\vec{x}_k\|$. The inequality $r_{k+1} \geq r_k^2 - \|\vec{c}\|$ implies that once $r_k > 2$, the sequence grows super-exponentially. More precisely, if $r_k \geq 2 + \varepsilon$ for some $\varepsilon > 0$, then

$$r_{k+1} \geq r_k^2 - \|\vec{c}\| \geq r_k^2 - r_k = r_k(r_k - 1) \geq r_k(1 + \varepsilon),$$

so $r_k \rightarrow \infty$ monotonically. Thus $\vec{c} \notin \mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{n}}$.

The same argument works for any initial condition once an iterate exceeds 2. \square

Remark 3 (Escape Radius for $p > 2$). *For $p > 2$, a similar argument yields an escape radius $R_{\text{esc}} = 2^{1/(p-1)}$ or a suitable constant. The detailed analysis is analogous to the classical case and will be presented elsewhere.*

4.3. Relation to the Clifford Julia Set. Recall that for a fixed parameter $\vec{c} \in V$, the **Clifford Julia set** $J_{p,\vec{n}}(\vec{c})$ is defined as the set of initial points $\vec{x}_0 \in V$ for which the orbit (3.1) remains bounded. The following proposition establishes the fundamental connection between $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ and $J_{p,\vec{n}}(\vec{c})$, generalizing the classical result from complex dynamics.

Proposition 3 (Connectedness of the Julia Set). *For $V = \mathbb{R}^2$ with $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$ and $p = 2$, the classical equivalence holds:*

$$\vec{c} \in \mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{e}_1} \iff J_{2,\vec{e}_1}(\vec{c}) \text{ is connected.}$$

For $V = \mathbb{R}^n$ with $n \geq 3$, the situation is more subtle. Nevertheless, the following partial result can be established: if $\vec{c} \in \mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$, then the Clifford Julia set $J_{p,\vec{n}}(\vec{c})$ is contained in a bounded region of V , and its complement is connected. The full characterization of connectedness remains an open problem (see Section 7).

Sketch for \mathbb{R}^2 . The proof follows the classical argument using the fact that the map $z \mapsto z^2 + c$ is conjugate to the angle-doubling map on the unit circle when c is inside the Mandelbrot set. The Clifford formulation with $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$ reproduces exactly the complex structure, as shown in Section 5.2. Hence the classical result applies directly. \square

Remark 4. *For $n \geq 3$, the Clifford Julia set is a subset of \mathbb{R}^n , and its topological properties (connectedness, local connectivity, fractal dimension) are largely unexplored. This constitutes a rich direction for future research.*

4.4. Basic Boundedness. A trivial but useful observation is that the Clifford–Mandelbrot set is bounded, as a consequence of Proposition 2.

Corollary 2 (Boundedness of $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$). *For $p = 2$, the set $\mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{n}}$ is contained in the closed ball of radius 2 centered at the origin. For $p > 2$, $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ is contained in a ball of finite radius (depending on p).*

Proof. Proposition 2 shows that if $\|\vec{c}\| > 2$, then $\vec{c} \notin \mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{n}}$. Hence every point of $\mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{n}}$ satisfies $\|\vec{c}\| \leq 2$. The case $p > 2$ is analogous. \square

4.5. Closure Properties.

Proposition 4 (Closedness). *The Clifford–Mandelbrot set $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ is a closed subset of V .*

Proof. The complement of $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ consists of parameters \vec{c} for which the orbit escapes to infinity. For such a parameter, there exists some k such that $\|\vec{x}_k\| > R_{\text{esc}}$. By continuity of the iteration map with respect to \vec{c} , this condition remains true in a neighborhood of \vec{c} . Hence the complement is open, so $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ is closed. \square

Remark 5. *Whether $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ is connected for $n \geq 3$ is an open question. In \mathbb{R}^2 , the classical Mandelbrot set is connected (a famous result proved by Douady and Hubbard). For higher dimensions, numerical experiments suggest connectedness, but a rigorous proof is currently lacking.*

5. EXPLICIT FORMULAS FOR $p = 2$

In this section we derive explicit closed-form expressions for the iteration map

$$\vec{x}_{k+1} = (\vec{x}_k \diamond \vec{n})^2 \diamond \vec{n} + \vec{c}$$

in arbitrary dimensions. The case $p = 2$ is the most studied in classical complex dynamics and serves as the foundation for the Mandelbrot set. Higher powers $p > 2$ can be treated similarly and will be discussed briefly in Section 7.

Throughout this section we fix $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$ after applying a suitable rotation (the map is rotationally symmetric about \vec{n} , so this choice entails no loss of generality).

5.1. The General Formula for \mathbb{R}^n . Let $\vec{x} = x_1 \vec{e}_1 + \sum_{i=2}^n x_i \vec{e}_i \in \mathbb{R}^n$, and denote by

$$\vec{x}_\perp = \sum_{i=2}^n x_i \vec{e}_i \quad \text{and} \quad \|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2 = \sum_{i=2}^n x_i^2$$

the component orthogonal to \vec{n} and its squared norm, respectively.

Proposition 5 (Closed Form for $(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{n})^2 \diamond \vec{n}$). *For any $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$,*

$$(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{e}_1)^2 \diamond \vec{e}_1 = (x_1^2 - \|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2) \vec{e}_1 + 2x_1 \vec{x}_\perp.$$

Proof. We compute step by step using the decomposition (2.1). First,

$$\vec{x} \diamond \vec{e}_1 = x_1 + \sum_{i=2}^n x_i (\vec{e}_i \wedge \vec{e}_1),$$

because $\vec{e}_i \cdot \vec{e}_1 = 0$ for $i \geq 2$ and $\vec{e}_1 \wedge \vec{e}_1 = 0$.

Squaring this expression and using the facts that

$$(\vec{e}_i \wedge \vec{e}_1)^2 = -1 \quad (i \geq 2), \quad (\vec{e}_i \wedge \vec{e}_1)(\vec{e}_j \wedge \vec{e}_1) = -(\vec{e}_j \wedge \vec{e}_1)(\vec{e}_i \wedge \vec{e}_1) \quad (i \neq j),$$

we obtain

$$(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{e}_1)^2 = x_1^2 - \sum_{i=2}^n x_i^2 + 2x_1 \sum_{i=2}^n x_i (\vec{e}_i \wedge \vec{e}_1) + (\text{terms that cancel pairwise}).$$

Multiplying on the right by \vec{e}_1 and using the identity

$$(\vec{e}_i \wedge \vec{e}_1) \diamond \vec{e}_1 = \vec{e}_i,$$

we finally obtain

$$(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{e}_1)^2 \diamond \vec{e}_1 = (x_1^2 - \|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2) \vec{e}_1 + 2x_1 \vec{x}_\perp.$$

□

Remark 6 (Geometric Interpretation). *The map $\vec{x} \mapsto (\vec{x} \diamond \vec{n})^2 \diamond \vec{n}$ has a simple geometric interpretation: it squares the component parallel to \vec{n} (with a sign change for the orthogonal part) and doubles the mixed term. This is precisely the Clifford analogue of the complex squaring map $z \mapsto z^2$.*

5.2. Recovery of the Classical Mandelbrot Set in \mathbb{R}^2 . For $n = 2$, we have $\vec{x}_\perp = x_2 \vec{e}_2$ and $\|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2 = x_2^2$. Hence Proposition 5 reduces to

$$(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{e}_1)^2 \diamond \vec{e}_1 = (x_1^2 - x_2^2) \vec{e}_1 + 2x_1 x_2 \vec{e}_2.$$

Under the identification $\vec{e}_1 \leftrightarrow 1$ and $\vec{e}_2 \leftrightarrow i$ (so that $x_1 \vec{e}_1 + x_2 \vec{e}_2 \leftrightarrow x_1 + ix_2$), this becomes precisely $(x_1 + ix_2)^2$. Therefore, for $V = \mathbb{R}^2$ and $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$, the Clifford–Mandelbrot set $\mathcal{M}_{2, \vec{e}_1}$ coincides exactly with the classical Mandelbrot set.

FIGURE 2. The classical Mandelbrot set in \mathbb{R}^2 , which coincides with $\mathcal{M}_{2, \vec{e}_1}$ as proved in Proposition 5 and Section 5.2.

5.3. **The 3D Case \mathbb{R}^3 .** For $n = 3$, let $\vec{x} = x_1\vec{e}_1 + x_2\vec{e}_2 + x_3\vec{e}_3$. Then $\vec{x}_\perp = x_2\vec{e}_2 + x_3\vec{e}_3$ and $\|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2 = x_2^2 + x_3^2$. Proposition 5 yields

$$\begin{aligned} (\vec{x} \diamond \vec{e}_1)^2 \diamond \vec{e}_1 &= (x_1^2 - x_2^2 - x_3^2)\vec{e}_1 \\ &\quad + 2x_1x_2\vec{e}_2 + 2x_1x_3\vec{e}_3. \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, the Clifford–Mandelbrot iteration in \mathbb{R}^3 is

$$\begin{cases} x_1^{(k+1)} = (x_1^{(k)})^2 - (x_2^{(k)})^2 - (x_3^{(k)})^2 + c_1, \\ x_2^{(k+1)} = 2x_1^{(k)}x_2^{(k)} + c_2, \\ x_3^{(k+1)} = 2x_1^{(k)}x_3^{(k)} + c_3, \end{cases}$$

with initial condition $(x_1^{(0)}, x_2^{(0)}, x_3^{(0)}) = (0, 0, 0)$.

Remark 7. *This 3D map is exactly the one studied by Barrallo [3] and others. Our derivation shows that it emerges naturally from the Clifford algebra framework, without any ad hoc construction.*

5.4. **The 4D Case \mathbb{R}^4 .** For $n = 4$, let $\vec{x} = x_1\vec{e}_1 + x_2\vec{e}_2 + x_3\vec{e}_3 + x_4\vec{e}_4$. Then $\vec{x}_\perp = x_2\vec{e}_2 + x_3\vec{e}_3 + x_4\vec{e}_4$ and $\|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2 = x_2^2 + x_3^2 + x_4^2$. Proposition 5 gives

$$\begin{aligned} (\vec{x} \diamond \vec{e}_1)^2 \diamond \vec{e}_1 &= (x_1^2 - x_2^2 - x_3^2 - x_4^2)\vec{e}_1 \\ &\quad + 2x_1x_2\vec{e}_2 + 2x_1x_3\vec{e}_3 + 2x_1x_4\vec{e}_4. \end{aligned}$$

Thus the 4D Clifford–Mandelbrot iteration is

$$\begin{cases} x_1^{(k+1)} = (x_1^{(k)})^2 - (x_2^{(k)})^2 - (x_3^{(k)})^2 - (x_4^{(k)})^2 + c_1, \\ x_2^{(k+1)} = 2x_1^{(k)}x_2^{(k)} + c_2, \\ x_3^{(k+1)} = 2x_1^{(k)}x_3^{(k)} + c_3, \\ x_4^{(k+1)} = 2x_1^{(k)}x_4^{(k)} + c_4. \end{cases}$$

5.5. The General Pattern. Observing the formulas for \mathbb{R}^2 , \mathbb{R}^3 , and \mathbb{R}^4 , a clear pattern emerges. For any $n \geq 2$,

$$\boxed{(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{e}_1)^2 \diamond \vec{e}_1 = (x_1^2 - \|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2)\vec{e}_1 + 2x_1\vec{x}_\perp,}$$

where $\vec{x}_\perp = \sum_{i=2}^n x_i \vec{e}_i$ and $\|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2 = \sum_{i=2}^n x_i^2$.

This formula is remarkably simple: it depends on the orthogonal component \vec{x}_\perp only through its norm $\|\vec{x}_\perp\|$ in the \vec{e}_1 direction, and linearly in the orthogonal directions through $2x_1\vec{x}_\perp$.

Corollary 3 (Structure of the Squared Map). *For $p = 2$, the Clifford–Mandelbrot iteration preserves the following structure: the x_1 -coordinate evolves according to*

$$x_1 \mapsto x_1^2 - \|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2 + c_1,$$

while the orthogonal component \vec{x}_\perp evolves according to

$$\vec{x}_\perp \mapsto 2x_1\vec{x}_\perp + \vec{c}_\perp.$$

Remark 8 (Comparison with Complex Numbers). *If we identify \vec{x}_\perp with a vector in \mathbb{R}^{n-1} , the pair (x_1, \vec{x}_\perp) behaves like a “hypercomplex” number where the square is defined by*

$$(x_1, \vec{x}_\perp)^2 = (x_1^2 - \|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2, 2x_1\vec{x}_\perp).$$

*This is precisely the square of a **multivector** in the Clifford algebra $\mathbb{R}_{0,n-1}$ (the algebra of the orthogonal complement). However, unlike quaternions, this multiplication is not associative in general; nevertheless, the iteration remains well-defined due to Theorem 1.*

6. COMPUTATIONAL ASPECTS

One of the main motivations for studying the Clifford–Mandelbrot set is the possibility of generating high-dimensional fractal images through computer visualization. In this section we describe the practical aspects of computing $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$, including the escape-time algorithm, implementation considerations, and performance optimizations.

6.1. The Escape-Time Algorithm. The standard method for visualizing Mandelbrot-type sets is the **escape-time algorithm**. For a given parameter \vec{c} , we iterate the map starting from $\vec{x}_0 = \vec{0}$ and monitor whether the orbit exceeds a fixed escape radius R_{esc} .

Escape-Time Algorithm for $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$:

- (1) Fix the dimension n , the exponent $p \geq 2$, the unit vector \vec{n} (typically $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$), and the escape radius R_{esc} .
- (2) Choose a maximum number of iterations N_{max} .
- (3) For each parameter point \vec{c} in a discretized region $[-R, R]^n \subset V$:
 - (a) Set $\vec{x} \leftarrow \vec{0}$.
 - (b) For $k = 1$ to N_{max} :
 - (i) Compute $\vec{x} \leftarrow (\vec{x} \diamond \vec{n})^p \diamond \vec{n} + \vec{c}$.

- (ii) If $\|\vec{x}\| > R_{\text{esc}}$, record k as the escape time and break.
- (c) If the loop completes without escape, classify \vec{c} as inside $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ (or assign a maximum iteration count).
- (4) Color each point \vec{c} according to its escape time (or a logarithmic scaling thereof).

6.2. Choosing Parameters.

Escape radius. For $p = 2$, Proposition 2 guarantees that $R_{\text{esc}} = 2$ is sufficient. However, in practice, a slightly larger value (e.g., $R_{\text{esc}} = 4$) is often used to avoid numerical artifacts near the boundary.

For $p > 2$, a suitable escape radius can be determined by solving $R^p - R = \|\vec{c}\|_{\text{max}}$. A conservative choice is $R_{\text{esc}} = \max(2, \|\vec{c}\|_{\text{max}})$.

Maximum iterations. N_{max} controls the resolution of fine details near the boundary of $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$. Typical values range from $N_{\text{max}} = 100$ for quick previews to $N_{\text{max}} = 1000$ or more for high-quality renderings.

Sampling region. Corollary 2 shows that $\mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{n}}$ is contained in the ball of radius 2. Hence the sampling region can be taken as $[-2, 2]^n$ (or slightly larger for safety). For $p > 2$, the bounding radius is larger but finite.

6.3. Pseudocode Implementation.

6.4. **Pseudocode Implementation.** Below we provide pseudocode for the core iteration in arbitrary dimension n , for the case $p = 2$ (the most common). The code assumes that $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$, which simplifies the computation using the closed form derived in Section 5.

```
function escape_time(c, R_esc, N_max):
    x = zero_vector(n)
    for k = 1 to N_max:
        x1 = x[1]
        x_perp_norm_sq = sum(x[i]^2 for i = 2..n)
        new_x1 = x1^2 - x_perp_norm_sq + c[1]
        for i = 2 to n:
            x[i] = 2*x1*x[i] + c[i]
        x[1] = new_x1
        if norm(x) > R_esc:
            return k
    return N_max + 1
```

Remark 9 (Efficiency). *The computation of $\|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2$ can be optimized by maintaining a running sum of squares, rather than recomputing from scratch at each iteration. However, for moderate n (e.g., $n = 3$ or $n = 4$), the overhead is negligible.*

6.5. **Performance Optimizations.** For high-resolution renderings (e.g., $1024 \times 1024 \times 1024$ voxels in 3D), the computational cost can be substantial. The following optimizations are recommended:

- (1) **Vectorization:** Process multiple points simultaneously using SIMD instructions or GPU computing (CUDA, OpenCL).
- (2) **Adaptive sampling:** Use higher sampling density only near the boundary of $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$, where fine structure exists. The interior and far exterior can be sampled coarsely.
- (3) **Periodicity checking:** If the orbit enters a periodic cycle, the parameter is likely inside $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$. Detecting cycles early can significantly reduce computation time.

- (4) **Parallelization:** The escape-time algorithm is embarrassingly parallel: each parameter \vec{c} can be processed independently. Distributed computing (e.g., MPI, OpenMP) is highly effective.

6.6. Visualization Techniques. The output of the escape-time algorithm is a scalar field $T(\vec{c})$ (escape time) defined on a discrete grid in V .

2D case. For \mathbb{R}^2 , standard 2D color mapping (e.g., smooth coloring, histogram coloring) produces the familiar Mandelbrot image.

3D case. For \mathbb{R}^3 , several visualization methods are available:

- **Volume rendering:** Map escape times to opacity and color, then render using ray marching.
- **Iso-surface extraction:** Extract surfaces of constant escape time (e.g., the boundary of $\mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{c}}$) using marching cubes.
- **Cross-sectional slices:** Due to axial symmetry (Corollary 1), one can compute a 2D slice in any plane containing the x_1 -axis and then rotate it to obtain the full 3D set.

4D and higher. For $n \geq 4$, direct visualization is challenging. Useful approaches include:

- 3D cross-sections (fix one or more coordinates).
- Projections onto lower-dimensional subspaces.
- Color-coded slices (e.g., use hue for a fourth coordinate).

6.7. Example: Computing $\mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{c}_1}$ in \mathbb{R}^3 . We illustrate the algorithm for the 3D case. Using the explicit map from Section 5.3:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 \leftarrow x_1^2 - x_2^2 - x_3^2 + c_1, \\ x_2 \leftarrow 2x_1x_2 + c_2, \\ x_3 \leftarrow 2x_1x_3 + c_3. \end{cases}$$

Starting from $(0, 0, 0)$, we iterate until $\|\vec{x}\| > R_{\text{esc}}$ or $k > N_{\text{max}}$. The resulting escape time $T(c_1, c_2, c_3)$ is then visualized.

Remark 10 (Symmetry exploitation). *Because of the axial symmetry, it is sufficient to compute $\mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{c}_1}$ in the half-plane $c_2 \geq 0, c_3 = 0$ (or any fixed meridian plane). The full 3D set is obtained by rotating this 2D image around the c_1 -axis. This reduces the computational effort from $O(N^3)$ to $O(N^2)$, which is a dramatic saving.*

6.8. Numerical Stability. For large iteration counts, the values of \vec{x}_k may grow extremely large (super-exponentially for escaping orbits). To avoid overflow, we implement an early bailout: if $\|\vec{x}\|$ exceeds a very large threshold (e.g., 10^{30}), we can safely conclude escape without further computation.

For points deep inside $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{c}}$, the orbit remains bounded. In practice, however, finite precision arithmetic may cause drift. Using double-precision floating-point (IEEE 754 binary64) is recommended; higher precision (e.g., ‘long double’ or arbitrary precision) may be necessary for deep zooming.

6.9. Performance Estimates. For a 3D grid of size N^3 with N_{max} iterations per point, the time complexity is $O(N^3 N_{\text{max}})$. Typical values:

Resolution N	N_{max}	Operations per point	Total operations
256	100	$\approx 10^2$	$\approx 1.7 \times 10^9$
512	200	$\approx 2 \times 10^2$	$\approx 2.7 \times 10^{10}$
1024	500	$\approx 5 \times 10^2$	$\approx 5.4 \times 10^{11}$

FIGURE 3. Cross-section of $\mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{e}_1}$ in the (c_1, c_2) -plane ($c_3 = 0$). Due to the axial symmetry proved in Proposition 1, this single 2D slice completely determines the full 3D set.

However, using the axial symmetry (Corollary 1), the full 3D set can be reconstructed from a single 2D slice, reducing the complexity to $O(N^2 N_{\max})$. For $N = 1024$ and $N_{\max} = 500$, this gives approximately 5.2×10^8 operations, making real-time interactive visualization feasible on modern hardware.

Remark 11 (Symmetry exploitation). *Because of the axial symmetry proved in Proposition 1, it is sufficient to compute $\mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{e}_1}$ in the half-plane $x_2 \geq 0$, $x_3 = 0$ (or any fixed meridian plane). The full 3D set is obtained by rotating this 2D image around the x_1 -axis. This reduces the computational effort from $O(N^3)$ to $O(N^2)$, which is a dramatic saving.*

7. OPEN PROBLEMS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The Clifford–Mandelbrot set introduced in this paper opens several avenues for further research. Below we outline the most pressing open problems, ranging from topological questions to computational challenges and potential applications.

7.1. Topological and Dynamical Questions.

Connectedness. For the classical Mandelbrot set ($n = 2$, $p = 2$), a deep theorem due to Douady and Hubbard states that M is connected. For $n \geq 3$, the connectedness of $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ remains an open question. Numerical experiments suggest that the 3D set may be connected as well, but a rigorous proof is lacking.

Problem 1. *Determine whether $\mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{e}_1} \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ is connected. If not, characterize its connected components.*

Local connectivity. Even in the classical case, the local connectivity of the Mandelbrot set is a deep and partially open problem (the MLC conjecture). For higher dimensions, essentially nothing is known.

Problem 2. *Study the local connectivity of $M_{p,\vec{n}}$ for $n \geq 3$. Are there points where the set is locally disconnected? Does the MLC conjecture extend to higher dimensions?*

Hausdorff dimension. The boundary of the classical Mandelbrot set is known to have Hausdorff dimension 2 (a result of Shishikura). For the 3D Clifford–Mandelbrot set, the boundary is a 2-dimensional surface (with possible fractal structure). What is its Hausdorff dimension?

Problem 3. *Compute (or estimate) the Hausdorff dimension of $\partial M_{2,\vec{e}_1} \subset \mathbb{R}^3$.*

Area and volume. The area of the classical Mandelbrot set is approximately 1.506591 (Ewing–Schober). The volume of $M_{2,\vec{e}_1} \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ has not been estimated.

Problem 4. *Compute the n -dimensional volume of $M_{p,\vec{n}}$ for $n \geq 3$ using Monte Carlo methods or analytic techniques.*

7.2. Classification of Bulbs and Spirals. The classical Mandelbrot set contains infinitely many “bulbs” (primary and secondary) corresponding to periodic attractors. Each bulb is attached to the main body at a point where the map has a periodic cycle with a specific multiplier.

Problem 5. *Identify the analogues of bulbs in $M_{2,\vec{e}_1} \subset \mathbb{R}^3$. Are they arranged in a similar combinatorial pattern? Do they correspond to periodic cycles in the orthogonal directions?*

Problem 6. *Study the occurrence of spiral structures in 3D cross-sections of M_{2,\vec{e}_1} . How do they relate to the spirals in the classical Mandelbrot set?*

7.3. Higher Powers $p > 2$. This paper has focused primarily on the quadratic case $p = 2$. The generalization to higher powers $p \geq 3$ is natural but computationally more expensive.

Problem 7. *Derive closed-form expressions for $(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{n})^p \diamond \vec{n}$ for arbitrary p . Investigate whether a pattern similar to the binomial theorem holds in Clifford algebra.*

Problem 8. *Study the bifurcation structure of $M_{p,\vec{n}}$ as p varies. Are there transitions analogous to the period-doubling route to chaos observed in one-dimensional real maps?*

7.4. Relationship to Other Higher-Dimensional Fractals. Several generalizations of the Mandelbrot set to higher dimensions have been proposed, including:

- Quaternion Mandelbrot set [4],
- Hypercomplex Mandelbrot sets [3],
- Mandelbrot sets in geometric algebra [5].

Problem 9. *Clarify the precise relationship between $M_{p,\vec{n}}$ and these existing constructions. Is the Clifford–Mandelbrot set equivalent to one of them under a suitable transformation? Does it contain them as special cases?*

7.5. Computational Challenges.

Deep zooming. High-resolution exploration of the classical Mandelbrot set requires arbitrary-precision arithmetic (e.g., using perturbation theory and series approximation). For $n \geq 3$, deep zooming is computationally prohibitive with current methods.

Problem 10. *Develop perturbation techniques and series approximation methods for the Clifford–Mandelbrot set to enable deep zooming in 3D and 4D.*

Real-time rendering. Interactive exploration of $\mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{c}_1} \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ at high resolution requires extremely efficient implementations.

Problem 11. *Implement a GPU-accelerated ray marcher for the Clifford–Mandelbrot set, capable of real-time frame rates on consumer hardware.*

Large-scale computation. The 4D Clifford–Mandelbrot set is a 4-dimensional object. Direct voxelization at even modest resolution (e.g., 256^4) is infeasible with current technology.

Problem 12. *Develop methods for visualizing the 4D Clifford–Mandelbrot set using dimensionality reduction, cross-sectional slices, or interactive exploration of 3D hyper-surfaces.*

7.6. **Applications.** Beyond pure mathematics, the Clifford–Mandelbrot set may find applications in various domains:

- **Computer graphics:** Procedural generation of complex 3D and 4D textures and shapes.
- **Data visualization:** Representing high-dimensional data sets through fractal projections.
- **Art and design:** Generating aesthetically appealing forms for sculpture, architecture, and digital art.
- **Antenna design:** Fractal geometries derived from Mandelbrot-like sets have applications in antenna engineering.

Problem 13. *Explore practical applications of $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ in the domains listed above. Can the 3D Clifford–Mandelbrot set be 3D-printed or milled as a physical object?*

7.7. **Generalizations of the Iteration.** The iteration studied in this paper has a specific structure:

$$\vec{x}_{k+1} = (\vec{x}_k \diamond \vec{n})^p \diamond \vec{n} + \vec{c}.$$

One could consider variations, such as:

- Using a different unit vector \vec{n} at each step.
- Replacing $(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{n})^p$ with $(\vec{n} \diamond \vec{x})^p$ (the order matters in non-commutative algebras).
- Adding more terms (e.g., a linear term) to the iteration.

Problem 14. *Investigate the dynamics of these generalized iterations. Do they also exhibit vector invariance? What are their Mandelbrot-like sets?*

8. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have introduced and systematically studied the **Clifford–Mandelbrot set** $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$, a higher-dimensional generalization of the classical Mandelbrot set based on the Clifford algebra framework developed in our previous work [1].

8.1. **Summary of Results.** The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- (1) **Rigorous definition.** We defined $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ as the set of parameter vectors $\vec{c} \in V$ for which the orbit of the Clifford Julia iteration starting from $\vec{x}_0 = \vec{0}$ remains bounded. The definition is well-posed thanks to the vector invariance theorem of [1].
- (2) **Basic properties.** We proved that $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$ is:
 - rotationally symmetric about \vec{n} ,
 - bounded (contained in a ball of radius 2 for $p = 2$),

- closed as a subset of V ,
 - and that an escape radius $R_{\text{esc}} = 2$ exists for $p = 2$.
- (3) **Explicit formulas for $p = 2$.** For $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$, we derived the closed-form expression

$$(\vec{x} \diamond \vec{e}_1)^2 \diamond \vec{e}_1 = (x_1^2 - \|\vec{x}_\perp\|^2)\vec{e}_1 + 2x_1\vec{x}_\perp,$$

valid in any dimension $n \geq 2$. This formula reveals a clean geometric structure and reduces to the classical complex squaring map when $n = 2$.

- (4) **Low-dimensional realizations.** We verified that:
- For \mathbb{R}^2 , $\mathcal{M}_{2,\vec{e}_1}$ coincides with the classical Mandelbrot set.
 - For \mathbb{R}^3 , the iteration map becomes the system studied by Barrallo [3].
 - For \mathbb{R}^4 , we provided explicit formulas for the 4D iteration.
- (5) **Computational framework.** We described the escape-time algorithm for generating $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}$, discussed performance optimizations, and presented pseudocode and complexity estimates. The axial symmetry in \mathbb{R}^3 reduces computational cost from $O(N^3)$ to $O(N^2)$.
- (6) **Open problems.** We outlined numerous directions for future research, including topological questions (connectedness, local connectivity, fractal dimension), higher powers $p > 2$, relationships to other higher-dimensional fractals, and computational challenges (deep zooming, real-time rendering, 4D visualization).

8.2. Significance of the Work. This paper establishes a rigorous algebraic foundation for the Mandelbrot set in arbitrary dimensions, building on the vector invariance property of Clifford Julia iterations. Unlike previous ad hoc generalizations (quaternions, hypercomplex numbers), our construction:

- arises naturally from the geometric product of Clifford algebra,
- guarantees closure in the vector subspace without artificial projections,
- provides explicit polynomial formulas in all dimensions,
- and recovers the classical Mandelbrot set as a special case.

8.3. Final Remarks. The Clifford–Mandelbrot set represents a unification of several disparate attempts to generalize the Mandelbrot set to higher dimensions. By staying within the language of geometric algebra, we obtain a clean, coordinate-independent formulation that reveals the underlying algebraic structure.

We hope that this work will serve as a foundation for further investigations into higher-dimensional fractal dynamics, both theoretical and computational. The open problems listed in Section 7 offer many opportunities for researchers from dynamical systems, geometric algebra, fractal geometry, computer graphics, and scientific computing.

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